

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE**Muhitdinova Ruksora,***English teacher of the secondary school*

Annotation: Today, there are several different methods of innovative educational technologies. If they are used to explain themes, the effectiveness of the lesson may be on top and students will be very interested to the lesson. In the given theoretical part of work it is necessary to pay attention on those basic statements in which the most essential parts of activity are reflected and generalized. That means the methodical principles underly teaching.

This article is about modern technologies in teaching a foreign language.

Keywords: grammar game “Umbrella”, modern technologies, information technology, communicative technology.

Lately the issue of using modern technologies in the educational process increased. It means not only new technical tools, but also a new forms and methods of teaching, new approach to learning. The main goal that we set for ourselves, using modern technologies in learning a foreign language is to show how technology can be effectively used to improve the quality of teaching foreign language students, the formation and development of their communicative culture, learning the practical mastery of a foreign language.

We are going to the new period of teaching foreign languages through new steps. Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his speech of June 15, 2017 year in Tashkent conference that was dedicated to issues of ensuring social justice, preserving the true essence and significance of our sacred religion of Islam, drew special attention to issues of educating the younger generation. These tasks place great responsibility on school, family, makhalla, and the entire community. Activities carried out in our country on improving all links in the sphere of education and upbringing-the system of preschool, school, secondary special and higher

education, constrictions of new and reconstruction of existing educational institutions will give its results in formation of young generation as harmoniously developed individuals[1].

And it is also required to use advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods and communicative media in the process of lessons of teaching foreign languages. There have been developed methods and requirements in Uzbekistan on the basis of Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR)

In order to assess teaching process, knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers. And also there have been created manuals (textbooks) for schools and colleges according to it. The study rooms were equipped with stands, new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning foreign language is also increasing day by day.[2, p.45-46]

However, all these should be supported by new teaching methods, which help to involve all students in the classroom in the activities and provide a good result. Let's consider some methods that can be used in the classroom.

GRAMMAR GAME UMBRELLA

Grammar:	Modals and present simple
Level:	Elementary to intermediate
Time:	30-40 minutes
Materials:	One large sheet of paper per student

In class

Ask a student to draw a picture on the board of a person holding an umbrella. The umbrella looks like this.

1. Explain to the class that this 'tulip-like' umbrella design is a new, experimental one.

2. Ask the students to work in small groups and brainstorm all the advantages and disadvantages of a new design. Ask them to use these sentence stems:

It/you can/can't...

It/you + present simple...

It/you will/won't...

It/you may/may not... For example: 'It is easy to control in a high wind', 'You can see where you're going with this umbrella' Give the students large sheets of paper and ask them to list the advantages and disadvantages in two columns.

3. Ask the students to move around the room and read each other's papers.

Individually they mark each idea as 'good', 'bad' or 'intriguing'.

4. Ask the student how many advantages they came up with and how many disadvantages. Ask the students to divide up into three groups according to which statement applies to them:

I thought mainly of advantages.

I thought of some of both.

I thought mainly of disadvantages.

5. Ask the three groups to come up with five to ten adjectives to describe their group state of mind and put these up on the board.

6. Round off the exercise by telling the class that when de Bono asked different groups of people to do this kind of exercise, it turned out that primary school children mostly saw advantages, business people had plenty of both while groups of teachers were the most negative.

Note

Advantages the students offered:

In a hot country you can collect rain water.

It won't drip round the edges.

You can use it for carrying shopping.

It's not dangerous in a crowd.

It's an optimistic umbrella.

It's easy to hold if two people are walking together.

With this umbrella you'll look special.

It'll take less floor space to dry.

This umbrella makes people communicate. They can see each other. You can paint this umbrella to look like a flower.

You'll get a free supply of ice if it hails[3].

As learning foreign languages is highly demanded today, using modern information and innovative technologies in the process of education brings efficient result. The effectiveness of innovative technologies is their proper and efficient use in the educational process.

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